

Small scale diversification with cereals, quinoa, pulses, etc, in local (organic) value chains

Problem

Cereals, quinoa and (new) pulses for local human consumption can diversify (organic) vegetable rotations. Between the idea to diversify rotations and the practice, lots of mistakes and setbacks often occur which could be avoided by planning beforehand.

Solution

Besides cultivation knowledge, it is recommended to make appropriate post-harvest equipment and facilities (e.g. for drying, cleaning and sorting) available beforehand. It is also recommended to explore profitable local value chains beforehand.

Outcome

Organic cereals and pulses for local human consumption diversify intensive organic vegetable rotations and are valorised within local value chains.

Practical recommendation

- Explore available literature, knowledge and experiences in your region, or in neighbouring regions with similar soil and climatic conditions (photo 1).
- Look for varieties and seeds appropriate for your conditions and intended purpose.
- Start with a small experimental plot in a garden or nearby field for the first test.
- Start the crop on your best suited soil and use appropriate machinery and cultivation techniques (sowing, weed control, etc),, in line with the available machinery on the farm. Do not test more than one factor into one experiment (i.e. a new crop and a new cultivation technique on the farm).
- After the harvest cereals and pulses have to be dried, cleaned and stored before delivery. These are critical processes that have to be planned before planting the crop. As cultivated areas and harvested volumes in vegetable farms are often small and commercial facilities are often at a large scale, specialised facilities are often needed.

Photo 1: Field visit with actors in the first organic soybean field in Flanders, July 2018, © Lieven Delanote, Inagro

Applicability box

Theme

Rotation, Organic, Value chain

Agronomic conditions

Not specific

Application time

Not specific

Required time

A step-by-step process over years

Period of impact

For as long as diversification continues

Equipment

Depends upon the diversification, but usually drying cleaning and sorting facilities

Best in

Farms with small scale arable production

Photo 2: Processor explains the required acceptance rules for raw materials at his production site to some delivering local farmers, January 2020, © An Jamart, Bioforum

- Local value chains provide opportunities to build up added value. Talk to each other about desired quality, certification and delivery (photo 2) in order to avoid misunderstanding or over-processing. Invest time to discuss shared values and ambitions.
- A fair price is needed to sustain the value chain over time. Current market prices are usually not profitable to small farmers in local value chains. The practice abstract 'tools for defining a fair price and strengthening crop diversification value chains' can help when discussing a fair relationship within your value chain (link below).
- Make appointments for regular conversations between actors in your value chain and to visit each other.

Further information

Further readings

- Practice abstract 'tools for defining a fair price and strengthening crop diversification value chains'

Weblinks

- <https://inagro.be/eiwitrijke-gewassen>
- <https://www.quinoalokaal.be/nl>

About this practice abstract and DiverIMPACTS

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DiverIMPACTS: The project is running from June 2017 to May 2022. The overall goal of DiverIMPACTS - Diversification through Rotation, Intercropping, Multiple Cropping, Promoted with Actors and value-Chains towards Sustainability - is to achieve the full potential of diversification of cropping systems for improved productivity, delivery of ecosystem services and resource-efficient and sustainable value chains.

Project website: www.diverimpacts.net

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